

NOTES

corresponding molar absorptivity 9.1×10^3 . The complex is deep yellow in colour with an absorption maximum at 450 nm which remains unaltered irrespective of the molar ratio of the components of the solution. This indicates the presence of only one complex in the solution under the conditions of study. The absorption by the reagent is also considerable at λ_{\max} of the complex (450 nm); this necessitated the use of reagent blank in the subsequent study. The absorbance vs. pH plot shows that the absorption of the complex remains maximum and constant between pH 9.5 and 12.2. Thus a pH around 10.5 was kept for spectrophotometric study. The absorption of the reagent remains practically unaltered in the pH range under investigation. The mole-ratio plot shows that two moles of PPA-QH per mole of copper are sufficient for full colour development; thus indicating that the metal and the ligand are present in 1:2 ratio in the complex. This was also confirmed by the method of continuous variations.

The system adheres to Beer's law up to 2.5 γ /ml of copper concentration and its sensitivity is 0.002 γ Cu/cm² for 0.001 absorbance. The value for its molecular extinction coefficient is calculated to be 3.15×10^4 .

Procedure for Determination of Copper: Take a suitable aliquot of copper solution (up to 25 γ /ml) in a 10 ml volumetric flask, add sufficient excess (nearly 10 to 15 times the molar excess of copper solution) of PPA-QH solution (in ethanol), 2 ml of buffer solution (pH around 10.5) followed by alcohol and water so that the final solution contains 50% (v/v) alcohol. Measure the absorbance at 450 nm against a reagent blank prepared under similar conditions.

Extraction Procedure in Presence of Interfering Ions: In presence of sodium perchlorate the complex is sufficiently extractable in *n*-butanol. The extractability in chloroform is poor. To determine copper in presence of interfering ions, the copper complex may be extracted. To a suitable aliquot of copper solution, add 10 to 15 molar excess of PPA-QH solution (in alcohol), 2 ml of buffer (to adjust pH around 10.5) and 2.5 ml of 50% (w/v) sodium perchlorate solution. The alcohol content of the solution is slowly evaporated on a water bath and the volume is made up to 10 ml with water. The solution is shaken with 10 ml of *n*-butanol for 1 hr. The absorbance of the organic layer is measured at 450 nm against a reagent blank prepared under identical conditions.

Interferences

Many of the ions precipitate at the high pH which is used here for studying copper complex with PPA-QH. To study the effect of foreign ions on the determination of copper using this reagent, the precipitated species, if any, is either centrifuged off or the extraction procedure adopted as outlined above, and the absorbance of the decanted or extracted solution is measured at 450 nm. The amounts of foreign ions (in γ /ml) tolerated in estimation of 0.5 γ /ml of copper at pH 10.5 are: 100 γ /ml of each of CH_3COO^- , NO_2^- , F^- , I^- , SO_4^{2-} , SO_3^{2-} , citrate, tartrate, BO_3^{3-} , Ag^+ , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , As^{3+} , Sb^{3+} , Sn^{2+} , Ce^{4+} , Th^{4+} , and

UO_2^{2+} ; 50 γ /ml of each of NO_3^- , Cl^- , Br^- , Al^{3+} and Mo^{6+} ; 25 γ /ml of each of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , and Ni^{2+} ; and 2 to 4 γ /ml of each of platinum metals.

Copper was successfully determined in a number of alloys viz., brass, gun metal and BCS 180 cupronickel. Traces of copper were correctly estimated when added to cadmium and zinc acetates (2 to 5 γ /25 ml).

Discussion

The sensitivity of the present reagent towards detection and determination of copper is excellent and is comparable to other tridentate hydrazones. Amongst the earlier developed hydrazones, quinoline-2-aldehyde-2-quinolyldiazine^{8,9} having the most extended π -bonding system seems to be the most sensitive for copper. The values for its copper complex are 4.7×10^4 (in nitrobenzene) and 5.8×10^4 (in benzene) while that of copper-PPA-QH complex is 3.15×10^4 . The drawback of the reagent lies in its use at high pH where many other ions are also precipitated, thus making the centrifugation or extraction necessary.

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Polarographic Determination of the Composition and Formation Constant of the Aspirinato-molybdenum (VI) Complex

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ASPIRIN (acetyl salicylic acid), a derivative of salicylic acid is well known as an effective chelating agent. Extensive work has been done on a number of metal chelates of aspirin. Aspirin complex with rubidium¹ has been reported in literature. Sahu and Bhattacharya² have investigated thallos complex of aspirin by conductometric measurements. Gour, *et. al*³ have investigated indium-aspirin anion system polarographically and found various complex species in solution.

Palercha and Gour⁴ have also polarographically studied aspirin complexes with cadmium, lead and copper, and reported 1:1 and 1:2 complexes for both lead and cadmium, and for copper 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 complexes. The present work has been undertaken with a view to establish the composition and to determine the formation constant of the aspirinato complex by using Kolthoff and Lingane⁵ equations.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of Analar quality Sodium molybdate which on analysis was found to have the formula $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Gelatin (0.01%) was used as a maximum suppressor and purified hydrogen was passed through each solution to remove dissolved oxygen. Doubly distilled mercury was used for DME.

Polarograms were obtained in the conventional manner using a recording type polarograph "PO₄ Radiometer Polariter". Measurement of pH was done on a Beckmann pH meter, using a combined glass calomel electrode. The drop time, sensitivity, damping and chart speed were kept constant throughout the operation. All the operations were carried out at room temperature.

A series of polarograms were obtained with different concentrations of the ligand. These exhibit a shift in the half wave potential of molybdenum (VI) towards a positive direction with increasing concentrations of the ligand. The changes in the $E_{1/2}$ when plotted against the logarithm of the corresponding ligand concentrations give a straight line, the slope of which gives the ratio of change in half wave potential and change in ligand concentration. This ratio has been used in the calculation of the formation constant⁶.

The reversibility of the electrode reaction was verified by plotting $\log_{10} \frac{(I_d - I)}{I}$ against the corresponding potential E , where I_d and I are the diffusion current and current at the applied potential E respectively.

In forming 1:2 complex two aspirinate anions replace two of the four coordinated oxygen atoms around the molybdenum (VI) atom in a tetrahedral structure. The formation constant of the complex is found to be 2.92×10^{-5} .

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Some New Uses of Ferroin as Redox Indicator

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THE use of ferroin as redox indicator in the dichrometric titration of hexacyanoferrate (II) and hydroquinone and the vanadometric titration of hydroquinone has not been reported till now. We have now been able to develop conditions under which this can be achieved and the results are in excellent agreement with those obtained by other methods.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. quality.

The following procedures are recommended for the titrations.

Dichrometric titration of hexacyanoferrate (II). Treat an aliquot of 0.1 *N* hexacyanoferrate (II) solution with enough 1:1 sulphuric acid, to give an overall acidity of 2-4 *M*, and 0.1 ml of 0.01 *M* ferroin. Dilute the mixture to 50 ml (or 100 ml if the amount of hexacyanoferrate (II) exceeds 4 moles) and titrate with 0.1 *N* potassium dichromate solution till the colour sharply changes from orange yellow to yellowish green.

Dichrometric titration of hydroquinone: Treat an aliquot of hydroquinone solution (0.1 *N*) with the requisite amount of 1:1 sulphuric acid, such that the overall acidity is 2-4 *M*, 0.5 ml of 1% hexacyanoferrate (IV) or 5-10 ml of 0.1 *N* uranium (VI) or 20 ml of 0.1 *N* iron (III) and 0.1 ml of 0.01 *M* ferroin. Dilute to 50 ml and titrate with 0.1 *N* potassium dichromate solution. The colour change at the end point is from orange red to yellowish green.

Vanadometric titration of hydroquinone: To the sample solution, containing 0.1 to 0.4 moles of hydroquinone, add enough sulphuric acid (1:1) to give an overall acidity of 5-6 *M*, 2.5-5.0 ml of syrupy phosphoric acid and 0.1 ml of 0.01 *M* ferroin. Dilute to 50 ml and titrate with 0.1 *N* sodium vanadate solution till the colour changes sharply from orange red to blue.

Results and Discussion

Dichrometric titration of hexacyanoferrate (II). This titration can also be performed in media of 3-5 *M* hydrochloric acid and 4-6 *M* phosphoric acid. The same procedure can be followed in titrations involving 0.01 *N* hexacyanoferrate (II) with 0.01 *N* potassium dichromate provided an indicator correction of 0.1 ml of 0.01 *N* dichromate is applied.

The reverse titrations, i.e., titrations of dichromate with hexacyanoferrate (II), using ferroin as indicator, also are possible under the same conditions of direct titration. In this connection, it may be mentioned that the method now developed for the reverse titration is advantageous over that reported [by Someya¹ who prescribes a potentiometric titration at elevated temperatures (40°-50°)].

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